

Leadership and Employee Performance: An Exploratory Study

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Abstract

Organizations have been facing many challenges regardless of their size, technology adopted, and highly strategic policies used. Additionally, the fast-paced technological advancements changed all aspects of life and the whole world has diversified the choices for job seekers. Due to the open global market business environment and subsequent global attractive job opportunities, the issue of employees’ job satisfaction has progressively gaining an increasing attention by both academicians as well as practitioners to retain the potential and loyal employees.

The current paper aims to study relationship among a) leadership and job performance and b) relationship between job characteristics and job performance. The research is exploratory in nature and adopted questionnaire method to collect data from employees of Information Technology(IT) organizations in Mysore city. Primary data is collected from 100 IT employees. The objective is attained by applying Correlation analysis using SPSS from which the following conclusions is drawn.

The Leadership style significantly influenced the ability of job performance but failed to influence employee organization citizenship behavior. A significant influence of job characteristic was found in nature of work, job flexibility and Job security.

Keywords: Leadership, OCB, Employee Performance, Job Attributes,

Introduction

The current changing, uncertain and competitive business environment has created great challenges for organizations striving to grow or even survive. In other words, currently, all kinds of organizations have been facing many challenges regardless of their size, technology adopted, and highly strategic policies used.

Additionally, the fast-paced technological advancements changed all aspects of life and the whole world has diversified the choices for job seekers. Due to the open global market business environment and subsequent global attractive job opportunities, the issue of employees’ job satisfaction has gained increasing attention among academicians and practitioners to retain the potential and loyal employees.

The necessity to retain talented and experienced employees has attracted both practitioners and academicians to pay cumulative attention to study the determinants of employees’ job satisfaction. In other words, scholarly attention has been directed to study the determinants of employees’ job satisfaction not just in terms of financial benefits but also in terms of other human aspects of jobs.

The influence of leadership on job performance, satisfaction, stress, and turnover intention has been well established. While leadership has an impact on organizations, departments, and teams, as well as work climate and atmosphere, leaders who want the best results should not rely on a single leadership style. An exploration of these and other variables has increased popularity of the Situational Leadership Theory (SLT).

Literature Review

Li-Chuan Chu, PhD, and Chun-Che Lai (2011), explores the effect of leadership style and job characteristics on job performance and examine the arbitrating effect of organization commitment on the leadership style, the job characteristics and the job performance as well as to provide the management suggestions according the research findings. This research also reveals that the more job autonomy, job importance, and job diversity exists, the stronger will be the ability to solve problems. Besides, the higher job autonomy for accountants exists, the higher passion of innovation happens. The arbitrating effect of organization commitment was found between transformational leadership and job performance, it indicates that organization commitment would be a mediator between transactional leadership and job performance.

Abdullah Kaid Al-Swidi, Mohd Kamal Mohd Nawawi & Asma Al-Hosam (2012), states that, transformational leadership has been proven to have a significant effect on the employees’ job satisfaction through enhancing the employees’ perception of empowerment. Regardless of this fact, the dynamic role of transformational style on enhancing the level of satisfaction among the empowered individuals has been momentarily neglected and the paper examine the joint effect of employees’ psychological empowerment and transformational leadership on the employees’ job satisfaction.

Lars Göran Wallgren and Jan Johansson Hanse (2010), states that job demand was positively related to perceived stress and the motivators mediate the relationship between job control and perceived stress. The results point to the importance of motivators among IT consultants in the framework of job stress and performance.

Objectives

1. To study the relationship among leadership style and job performance.
2. To understand the relationship between job characteristics and job performance.

Research Methodology

Data Collection

Primary data is congregated through the method of questionnaire. The sample size consists of 100 respondents employed in different IT organizations situated in Mysore City.

Conceptual Model

Formulation of Hypothesis

- H0: Changes in nature of work will have a significant positive correlation with OCB
- H1: Changes in nature of work will not have a significant positive correlation with OCB
- H0: Changes in nature of work will have a significant positive correlation with employee job satisfaction
- H2: Changes in nature of work will not have a significant positive correlation with employee job satisfaction
- H0: Job flexibility will have positive correlation with OCB
- H3: Job flexibility will not have positive correlation with OCB
- H0: Job flexibility will have a positive correlation with Job Satisfaction
- H4: Job flexibility will not have a positive correlation with Job Satisfaction
- H0: Job security and employee OCB are positively correlated
- H5: Job security and employee OCB are not positively correlated
- H0: Job security is positively correlated with Job Satisfaction
- H6: Job security is not positively correlated with Job Satisfaction
- H0: Leadership and Job Satisfaction are strongly positively correlated
- H7: Leadership and Job Satisfaction are not strongly positively correlated
- H0: Leadership will have a significant positive correlation with OCB
- H8: Leadership will not have a significant positive correlation with OCB

Results

Factor Analysis

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy		.637
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	1842.541
	Df	528
	Sig.	.000

Total Variance Explained

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	7.436	22.533	22.533	7.436	22.533	22.533	3.899	11.815	11.815
2	3.072	9.309	31.842	3.072	9.309	31.842	3.868	11.720	23.535
3	2.689	8.149	39.991	2.689	8.149	39.991	2.463	7.463	30.998
4	2.204	6.679	46.670	2.204	6.679	46.670	2.459	7.450	38.448
5	1.803	5.463	52.133	1.803	5.463	52.133	2.330	7.060	45.508

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6	1.623	4.917	57.050	1.623	4.917	57.050	2.021	6.124	51.632
7	1.528	4.631	61.681	1.528	4.631	61.681	1.929	5.845	57.477
8	1.273	3.856	65.537	1.273	3.856	65.537	1.699	5.148	62.625
9	1.152	3.490	69.028	1.152	3.490	69.028	1.491	4.519	67.144
10	1.100	3.334	72.362	1.100	3.334	72.362	1.424	4.315	71.459
11	1.037	3.142	75.504	1.037	3.142	75.504	1.335	4.044	75.504
12	.915	2.773	78.277						
13	.871	2.641	80.918						
14	.716	2.168	83.086						
15	.684	2.074	85.160						
16	.661	2.003	87.163						
17	.555	1.681	88.844						
18	.486	1.472	90.316						
19	.466	1.412	91.727						
20	.441	1.335	93.063						
21	.340	1.030	94.093						
22	.321	.974	95.066						
23	.244	.740	95.806						
24	.222	.672	96.478						
25	.201	.609	97.087						
26	.190	.576	97.663						
27	.166	.502	98.165						
28	.144	.435	98.600						
29	.132	.399	98.999						
30	.110	.332	99.331						
31	.100	.302	99.633						
32	.069	.208	99.841						
33	.053	.159	100.000						

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Correlations

		VAR00024	VAR00025	VAR00026	VAR00027	VAR00028	VAR00029	VAR00030	VAR00031	VAR00032	VAR00033
VAR00001	Pearson Correlation	.008	.071	.189	-.091	-.085	.092	.189	.082	.187	.086
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.938	.484	.060	.369	.400	.363	.059	.420	.063	.392
	N	100	100	100	100	100	99	100	100	100	100
VAR00002	Pearson Correlation	.033	-.031	.007	.047	.215*	-.014	.113	.084	-.024	-.023
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.744	.763	.942	.641	.032	.890	.264	.406	.816	.822
	N	100	100	100	100	100	99	100	100	100	100
VAR00004	Pearson Correlation	.032	.078	.027	.104	-.009	-.087	.124	.127	.075	.008
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.751	.442	.791	.301	.931	.394	.218	.210	.460	.937
	N	100	100	100	100	100	99	100	100	100	100

VAR00004	Pearson Correlation	-.052	.033	.164	.179	-.006	-.045	.075	-.023	.036	-.027
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.612	.743	.104	.076	.950	.661	.462	.823	.722	.795
	N	99	99	99	99	99	98	99	99	99	99
VAR00005	Pearson Correlation	-.068	.176	.022	.180	-.032	.118	.030	.067	.080	.013
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.502	.080	.825	.073	.749	.244	.766	.510	.426	.898
	N	100	100	100	100	100	99	100	100	100	100
VAR00006	Pearson Correlation	.056	.105	.257**	.401**	-.325**	.012	.079	.027	.054	-.065
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.578	.297	.010	.000	.001	.904	.432	.791	.595	.520
	N	100	100	100	100	100	99	100	100	100	100
VAR00008	Pearson Correlation	-.001	.132	.359**	.160	-.015	.128	.183	.114	.233*	.130
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.989	.189	.000	.112	.883	.206	.069	.259	.020	.199
	N	100	100	100	100	100	99	100	100	100	100
VAR00008	Pearson Correlation	-.086	.126	.488**	.168	-.032	-.066	.081	-.012	.096	.053
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.395	.210	.000	.096	.750	.514	.420	.909	.343	.598
	N	100	100	100	100	100	99	100	100	100	100
VAR00009	Pearson Correlation	.094	.012	.227*	-.059	.096	.170	.134	.254*	.211*	.093
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.352	.905	.023	.561	.342	.093	.182	.011	.035	.355
	N	100	100	100	100	100	99	100	100	100	100
VAR00011	Pearson Correlation	.131	.036	.314**	.209*	-.072	.102	.209*	.161	.236*	.251*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.193	.725	.001	.037	.475	.316	.037	.110	.018	.012
	N	100	100	100	100	100	99	100	100	100	100
VAR00011	Pearson Correlation	-.022	-.017	.208*	.271**	.000	.176	.137	.057	.213*	.053
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.829	.863	.038	.006	.998	.082	.175	.571	.033	.603
	N	100	100	100	100	100	99	100	100	100	100
VAR00012	Pearson Correlation	-.034	.048	.209*	.090	.011	.361**	.257**	.176	.122	.265**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.733	.638	.037	.372	.915	.000	.010	.080	.227	.008
	N	100	100	100	100	100	99	100	100	100	100
VAR00015	Pearson Correlation	-.164	.081	-.067	.113	.167	.330**	.215*	.219*	.117	.146
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.103	.426	.508	.264	.097	.001	.032	.028	.247	.148
	N	100	100	100	100	100	99	100	100	100	100
VAR00015	Pearson Correlation	-.197*	.448**	.176	.129	-.011	.185	-.039	.095	.165	.067
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.049	.000	.080	.200	.910	.067	.703	.348	.101	.509
	N	100	100	100	100	100	99	100	100	100	100
VAR00015	Pearson Correlation	.063	.400**	.098	-.028	.052	.153	.035	.066	.071	.042
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.532	.000	.332	.779	.606	.130	.728	.513	.482	.675
	N	100	100	100	100	100	99	100	100	100	100
VAR00017	Pearson Correlation	.058	.180	.344**	.367**	.063	.172	.272**	.308**	.289**	.273**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.569	.073	.000	.000	.532	.088	.006	.002	.004	.006
	N	100	100	100	100	100	99	100	100	100	100

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VAR00017	Pearson Correlation	.004	.308**	.267**	.262**	-.104	.280**	.280**	.262**	.287**	.298**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.971	.002	.007	.008	.305	.005	.005	.008	.004	.003
	N	100	100	100	100	100	99	100	100	100	100
VAR00018	Pearson Correlation	.003	.419**	.040	.016	-.213*	.130	-.073	-.062	-.135	-.108
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.979	.000	.695	.875	.033	.201	.469	.542	.181	.287
	N	100	100	100	100	100	99	100	100	100	100
VAR00019	Pearson Correlation	-.049	.278**	.336**	.293**	-.028	.272**	.356**	.266**	.354**	.329**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.627	.005	.001	.003	.785	.006	.000	.008	.000	.001
	N	100	100	100	100	100	99	100	100	100	100
VAR00020	Pearson Correlation	-.082	.377**	.395**	.202*	.119	.299**	.235*	.195	.291**	.179
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.419	.000	.000	.043	.237	.003	.019	.052	.003	.075
	N	100	100	100	100	100	99	100	100	100	100
VAR00021	Pearson Correlation	.176	.086	.467**	.371**	-.194	.090	.230*	.149	.310**	.300**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.080	.393	.000	.000	.053	.374	.021	.139	.002	.002
	N	100	100	100	100	100	99	100	100	100	100
VAR00022	Pearson Correlation	.186	.078	.453**	.492**	-.141	.190	.451**	.322**	.390**	.428**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.064	.438	.000	.000	.162	.059	.000	.001	.000	.000
	N	100	100	100	100	100	99	100	100	100	100
VAR00023	Pearson Correlation	.231*	.316**	.442**	.435**	.016	.034	.281**	.194	.318**	.295**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.021	.001	.000	.000	.871	.740	.005	.053	.001	.003
	N	100	100	100	100	100	99	100	100	100	100
VAR00024	Pearson Correlation	1	.001	-.036	.087	.183	-.186	.028	.073	.075	.126
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.989	.719	.392	.068	.066	.786	.468	.456	.211
	N	100	100	100	100	100	99	100	100	100	100
VAR00025	Pearson Correlation	.001	1	.137	.170	-.038	.156	.064	.154	.187	.196
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.989		.173	.092	.706	.122	.528	.125	.062	.051
	N	100	100	100	100	100	99	100	100	100	100
VAR00026	Pearson Correlation	-.036	.137	1	.364**	.141	.196	.401**	.372**	.400**	.407**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.719	.173		.000	.163	.051	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	100	100	100	100	100	99	100	100	100	100
VAR00029	Pearson Correlation	.087	.170	.364**	1	.023	.018	.259**	.190	.308**	.222*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.392	.092	.000		.824	.863	.009	.058	.002	.027
	N	100	100	100	100	100	99	100	100	100	100
VAR00029	Pearson Correlation	.183	-.038	.141	.023	1	.071	-.018	.120	.010	-.055
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.068	.706	.163	.824		.483	.860	.233	.921	.584
	N	100	100	100	100	100	99	100	100	100	100
VAR00029	Pearson Correlation	-.186	.156	.196	.018	.071	1	.551**	.513**	.558**	.425**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.066	.122	.051	.863	.483		.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	99	99	99	99	99	99	99	99	99	99

VAR00030	Pearson Correlation	.028	.064	.401**	.259**	-.018	.551**	1	.709**	.696**	.728**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.786	.528	.000	.009	.860	.000		.000	.000	.000
	N	100	100	100	100	100	99	100	100	100	100
VAR00031	Pearson Correlation	.073	.154	.372**	.190	.120	.513**	.709**	1	.687**	.679**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.468	.125	.000	.058	.233	.000	.000		.000	.000
	N	100	100	100	100	100	99	100	100	100	100
VAR00032	Pearson Correlation	.075	.187	.400**	.308**	.010	.558**	.696**	.687**	1	.725**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.456	.062	.000	.002	.921	.000	.000	.000		.000
	N	100	100	100	100	100	99	100	100	100	100
VAR00033	Pearson Correlation	.126	.196	.407**	.222*	-.055	.425**	.728**	.679**	.725**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.211	.051	.000	.027	.584	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	100	100	100	100	100	99	100	100	100	100

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Discussion

1. The nature of work and OCB share a positive relation among themselves with a correlation of 0.938 which is a strong positive correlation. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted.
2. There exists a positive correlation of 0.890 between nature of work and employee job satisfaction. Hence there exists a strong positive relation to prove the null hypothesis
3. The null hypothesis has been proved, thus there exist positive correlation of 0.578 between the job flexibility and OCB.
4. Job flexibility and OCB share a strong positive correlation of 0.904 and therefore proves the null hypothesis.
5. The null hypothesis has been accepted as there exists a positive correlation of 0.829 between Job security and OCB.
6. Job security and Job satisfaction are positively correlated with 0.728 which proves the null hypothesis.
7. Leadership in the organization can influence the employee job satisfaction as they both are positively correlated at the level of 0.971 which in turn proves the null hypothesis.
8. Leadership does not have any correlation with employee OCB as the correlation is 0.006 which proves the alternative hypothesis to be true.

Implications for Research

The entire hypotheses were accepted except the last one where there is a relationship between leadership and employee OCB. Considering this, companies should focus on improving their job characteristics and leadership styles to improve the individual as well as overall organizational productivity. No one single leadership style has been proved to be ideal, leaders should adopt multiple leadership styles in order to become an ideal leader by adopting Situational Leadership Style.

Study Limitations

The reason for the variables that did not account for the positive influence of job characteristics and leadership on job performance is identified due to time constraints. This can be taken forward for further research. The study focused exclusively on the effects of some variables of job

characteristics and leadership on job performance among the organization. Future research can consider the effects of other job characteristics of the work place.

Conclusion

Leadership style significantly influenced the ability of job performance but failed to have stimulus on the employee organization citizenship behavior. A significant effect of job characteristic was found in nature of work, job flexibility and also Job security.

References/Bibliography

1. Li-Chuan Chu, PhD, and Chun-Che Lai A Research on the Influence of Leadership Style and Job Characteristics on Job Performance among Accountants of County and City Government in Taiwan, Public Personnel Management Volume 40 No. 2 Summer 2011.
2. Abdullah Kaid Al-Swidi, Mohd Kamal Mohd Nawawi & Asma Al-Hosam- Is the Relationship between Employees’ Psychological Empowerment and Employees’ Job Satisfaction Contingent on the Transformational Leadership?, Asian Social Science, Vol. 8, No. 10; August 2012.
3. Lars Göran Wallgren and Jan Johansson Hanse, The Impact of Job Characteristics and Motivators on Perceived Stress Among Information Technology (IT) Consultants, The Ergonomics Open Journal, 2010, 3, 25-3.
4. Jui-Chen Chen, Colin Silverthorne, Leadership & Organization Development Journal Emerald Article: Leadership effectiveness, leadership style and employee Readiness, Leadership & Organization Development Journal Vol. 26 No. 4, 2005 pp. 280-288.
5. Abdullah Kaid Al-Swidi, Mohd Kamal Mohd Nawawi1 & Asma Al-Hosam - Is the Relationship between Employees’ Psychological Empowerment and Employees’ Job Satisfaction Contingent on the Transformational Leadership? A Study on the Yemeni Islamic Banks, Asian Social Science Vol. 8, No. 10; August 2012.
6. Lars Göran Wallgren and Jan Johansson Hanse - The Impact of Job Characteristics and Motivators on Perceived Stress Among Information Technology (IT) Consultants, The Ergonomics Open Journal, 2010, 3, 25-31.
7. Johanim Johari, Daratul Ambia Che Mit, and Khulida Kirana Yahya - Construct Validation of the Job Characteristics Scale in the Malaysian Public Service Setting, International Review of Business Research Papers Vol. 5, No. 3, April 2009, Pp. 58-71.